

Supplementary Material

for "Multi-Feature Membership Analysis for Tabular Regression Models: Towards Data Sovereignty"

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Introduction

This supplementary material accompanies the full paper "*Multi-Feature Membership Analysis for Tabular Regression Models: Towards Data Sovereignty*" (ECAI 2025). It provides extended methodological details, additional experimental results, extended analysis, and supporting tables and figures referenced in the main text. It is available at DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16942609.

S1. Runtime Analysis of Feature Extraction

To assess MFMA’s computational feasibility, we measured feature extraction runtimes on several datasets and model types using a 4-core/16GB setup. Each experiment trained 3 shadow models on 80% of the data. AUG used 3 noise levels with 16 augmentations per record. MVA masked each of the top 3 important features in turn.

Table 1 summarizes the average per-record runtime for each feature group, as well as the total runtime for the full extraction process as shown in Equation 1. Despite the inclusion of multiple augmentations and behavior-based features, extraction times remained practical across all datasets. Notably, larger datasets such as *Census* benefited from higher parallel efficiency and showed even faster per-record extraction. These results indicate that MFMA can be applied efficiently to datasets of varying scales and complexities.

$$\text{Total Time} = N_{\text{SM}} \times N_{\text{records}} \times (T_{\text{AUG}} \times N_{\text{noise}} \times N_{\text{aug}} + T_{\text{MVA}} \times N_{\text{mva}} + T_{\text{EV}}) \quad (1)$$

where:

- N_{SM} is the number of shadow models,
- N_{records} is the number of records in the dataset,
- $T_{\text{AUG}}, T_{\text{MVA}}, T_{\text{EV}}$ are the per-record extraction times for AUG, MVA, and EV features respectively,
- N_{noise} is the number of noise levels used in augmentation,
- N_{aug} is the number of augmentations per noise level,
- N_{mva} is the number of manipulated features for MVA.

Table 1: Runtime analysis for feature extraction across dataset-model combinations.

Metric	House – XGB	House – RF	Census – XGB	Census – RF
# Records	1,168	1,168	8,000	8,000
AUG time / record (ms)	0.12	0.48	0.07	0.46
MVA time / record (ms)	0.51	2.04	0.41	1.87
EV time / record (ms)	18.9	0.09	19.3	0.07
Avg time / record (ms)	26.3	29.3	24.2	27.7
Total time (sec)	92.1	103	580	665

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S2. Noise Robustness – Detailed Extraction Process

To illustrate the detailed extraction process for the noise robustness feature, Figure 1 presents the evolutionary search scheme used to identify minimal input perturbations that induce a targeted output shift.

Figure 1: Extension to Figure 3 from the main paper: Evolutionary strategy used to identify minimal input perturbation causing a defined output shift in the regression model.

S3. Noise Robustness Analysis

In order to better understand why the Noise Robustness (NR) feature did not improve attack performance, we analyzed the perturbation magnitudes required to shift the model’s predictions by a fixed target delta.

Figure 2: Distribution of the inverse perturbation magnitude (i.e., NR feature) for training and test samples across two datasets. The significant overlap between the distributions suggests limited separability between members and non-members based on this feature.

Figure 2 shows the distribution of the inverse perturbation magnitude (i.e., the NR feature) across training and test samples for two target deltas. As seen, the distributions of NR for train and test samples overlap significantly, indicating that the feature does not provide sufficient discriminative power. Unlike other behavioral features that tend to highlight confidence or stability differences between train and test points, the NR feature yields similar values across both groups, reducing its effectiveness for classification.

Figure 3: Scatter plot of perturbation magnitude vs. predicted values for training and test samples. The intermixing of red (test) and blue (train) points illustrates the weak discriminative power of the NR feature.

Figure 3 further illustrates the weak separability: when plotting the perturbation magnitude against the predicted value, train and test samples are largely intermixed with no clear pattern or boundary that could aid a classifier. This suggests that the model’s sensitivity to perturbations is not meaningfully different between members and non-members, making NR a poor standalone indicator for membership.

These findings highlight that while the concept of robustness-based inference is theoretically sound, its utility in practice—especially in regression tasks over tabular data—is limited without additional contextual or ensemble signals.

S4. Noise Sensitivity Analysis

Analysis of Noise Sensitivity (NS) Feature. To understand why the Noise Sensitivity (NS) feature did not improve attack performance, we conducted a targeted analysis of how input perturbations affect model predictions. In this setup, we applied noise of increasing magnitude to individual records and measured the resulting change in prediction. Importantly, for each record, we compared the sensitivity in two scenarios: when the record was part of the model’s training set (member) and when it was not (non-member), keeping the rest of the training data unchanged to isolate the impact of that specific record.

Figure 4 presents the results for two different parameterizations of the NS extraction algorithm, demonstrating consistency in the observed patterns. The large plots on the left show the average change in prediction across all perturbed records as a function of noise magnitude. The curves for member and non-member records closely overlap, indicating that on average, there is little distinction in sensitivity between the two groups. The smaller plots illustrate the prediction changes for individual sample records. While there are isolated cases where a member and non-member show divergent behavior (e.g., Record #609 in the first figure), in most examples the response curves are nearly identical or inconsistent across records. This suggests that the model’s sensitivity to input perturbation is largely uniform and not significantly influenced by whether a record was part of the training set.

We attribute this behavior to the inherently challenging nature of tabular data, where the relationship between features and predictions is often irregular and noisy. In such settings, even records that respond strongly to perturbation may not be outliers, but rather valid samples from underrepresented or highly variable subpopulations. This issue is further amplified when using a fixed noise level for all records, as done in NS, where the same perturbation might be negligible for some records, perceived as noise for others, or even resemble legitimate unseen data points. As a result, the NS feature fails to provide a consistent and reliable signal for membership inference.

(a) NS analysis with parameter set A.

(b) NS analysis with parameter set B.

Figure 4: Analysis of the NS feature. Each large plot on the left shows the average prediction change as a function of noise magnitude across all evaluated records. Smaller plots display the change in prediction for selected records under two conditions: when the record was part of the training set (blue) and when it was not (orange), with the rest of the training set held constant. Across both parameterizations, the average curves for members and non-members nearly overlap, and most individual cases show no consistent difference. This indicates that NS fails to capture reliable membership-related variance in model sensitivity.

S5. Pairwise Correlation Matrix of Attack Features

To assess potential redundancy and dependencies among the attack features, we computed the pairwise correlation matrix across all features used in the MFMA framework. The analysis was performed on a representative experimental setting using the HOUSE dataset and a Random Forest target model.

As shown in Figure 5, augmentation-based features (those prefixed with `aug_preds_`) exhibit strong internal correlation, particularly when derived from the same noise level. For example, `aug_preds_var_1` and `aug_preds_range_1` show a correlation above 0.9, indicating partial redundancy.

In contrast, features from different families—including error-based (`error`), missing-based (`missing_preds_*`), and ensemble-based (`ens_var_*`)—demonstrate low correlation with one another and with the augmentation group. This supports the interpretation that each feature family captures distinct behavioral aspects of the model, reinforcing the benefit of combining them for more effective membership inference.

Figure 5: Pairwise correlation matrix of attack features. Strong intra-group correlation is observed within augmentation-based features, while other groups remain largely uncorrelated.